

A Collatz-type dynamical system on Eisenstein integers

Cycle classification by double resonance and exhaustive itinerary enumeration

Marc Lebel — March 2026

Abstract. We introduce an accelerated Collatz-type map T^* on the Eisenstein integers $Z[\omega]$, using the prime $\pi = 1 - \omega$ (of norm 3) as divisor. *Theorem 1* [proved]: the only nonzero fixed points are $z = \pm 2\omega$. *Theorem 2* [proved]: the norm of the cycle denominator $\pi^K - 2^m$ satisfies an explicit formula; a small denominator requires simultaneous size resonance ($K/m \sim \log 4 / \log 3$) and phase alignment ($K \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$). *Theorem 3* [computer-assisted]: for $(m, K) = (19, 24)$, there exist exactly 12 cycles, forming 6 opposite pairs. *Theorem 4* [partially computer-assisted]: for $(m, K) = (28, 36)$, the two detected cycles are certified; a heuristic predicts no others. Convergence is observed on 10^6 points with zero divergence.

1. Algebraic framework

Let $\omega = e^{2\pi i/3}$ and $Z[\omega]$ the Eisenstein integers. An element $z = a + b\omega$ has norm $N(z) = a^2 - ab + b^2$. Set $\pi = 1 - \omega$, the Eisenstein prime above 3, with $N(\pi) = 3$. The quotient $Z[\omega]/(\pi) \sim F_3 = \{0, 1, -1\}$, with class determined by $(a+b) \pmod{3}$. Division by π : $z/\pi = ((2a-b)/3, (a+b)/3)$.

2. The dynamics T^*

Definition. The accelerated Eisenstein-Collatz map $T^* : Z[\omega] \rightarrow Z[\omega]$:

$$\begin{aligned} T^*(z) &= z / \pi^{v(z)} \quad \text{if } z \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi} \\ T^*(z) &= (2z - 2) / \pi^{v(2z-2)} \quad \text{if } z \equiv 1 \pmod{\pi} \\ T^*(z) &= (2z + 2) / \pi^{v(2z+2)} \quad \text{if } z \equiv -1 \pmod{\pi} \end{aligned}$$

with $T^*(0) = 0$ and $T^*(\pm 1) = 0$. After one step, all nonzero orbits enter $X = \{z : v_\pi(z) = 0\} \cup \{0\}$.

3. Anti-involution

Proposition 1 [proved]. $T^*(-z) = -T^*(z)$ for all primitive z . Cycles come in opposite pairs $\{C, -C\}$. For odd-period cycles, $C \neq -C$ as sets.

4. Fixed points

Theorem 1 [proved]. The only nonzero fixed points of T^* are $z = \pm 2\omega$.

Proof. A primitive fixed point satisfies $z(2 - \pi^k) = 2\epsilon$. Norms: $N(z) \cdot N(2 - \pi^k) = 4$. For $k=1$: $N(2 - \pi) = N(1 + \omega) = 1$, $N(z) = 4$, $z = \pm 2\omega$. For $k=2$: $N(2 - \pi^2) = 19 > 4$. For $k \geq 3$: $N > 4$.

5. Norm formula and phase obstruction

Theorem 2 [proved]. For all $m, K \geq 1$:

$$N(\pi^K - 2^m) = 3^K + 4^m - 2^{m+1} \cdot 3^{K/2} \cdot \cos(K\pi/6)$$

Proof. $\pi = \sqrt{3} \cdot e^{-i\pi/6}$, so $\pi^K = 3^{K/2} \cdot e^{-iK\pi/6}$. Then $N(\pi^K - 2^m) = |\pi^K - 2^m|^2 = 3^K - 2^{m+1} \cdot 3^{K/2} \cdot \cos(K\pi/6) + 4^m$.

Corollary 1 (Phase obstruction) [proved]. If K is not 0 mod 12, then $N(\pi^K - 2^m) \geq 4^{m-1}$.

Proof. Set $r = 3^{K/2}/2^m$ and $\theta = K\pi/6$. Then $N/4^m = f(r) = r^2 - 2r \cdot \cos(\theta) + 1$.

Case 1: $\cos(\theta) \leq 0$ ($K \equiv 3, 9 \pmod{12}$). Then $f(r) \geq r^2 + 1 \geq 1$, so $N \geq 4^m$.

Case 2: $\cos(\theta) > 0$, $\theta \neq 0$ ($K \equiv 1, 2, 10, 11 \pmod{12}$). $f(r) = (r - \cos(\theta))^2 + \sin^2(\theta) \geq \sin^2(\theta)$. The minimum $\sin^2(\theta)$ over these residues is $\sin^2(\pi/6) = 1/4$, attained at $K \equiv 1, 11 \pmod{12}$. Hence $N \geq 4^m/4 = 4^{m-1}$.

The bound is tight: $N/4^m \rightarrow 1/4$ along sequences with $K = 1 \pmod{12}$ and $3^{K/2}/2^m \rightarrow \sqrt{3}/2$.

Corollary 2 (Double resonance). Small denominators require both: (i) **size resonance** $K/m \sim \log 4/\log 3$, and (ii) **phase alignment** $K = 0 \pmod{12}$, so $\pi^k = 3^{K/2}$ in \mathbb{Z} and $N = (3^{K/2} - 2^m)^2$.

m	K	K mod 12	D	N(D)	Phase	Cycles
19	24	0	7 153	5.1×10^7	aligned	12 (Thm 3)
28	36	0	1.19×10^8	1.4×10^{16}	aligned	2 (Thm 4)
3	4	4	—	$\geq 4^2$	blocked	0
42	53	5	—	$\geq 4^{41}$	blocked	0 expected

6. Itinerary theory

Each primitive step has the form $z \rightarrow (2z - 2\epsilon)/\pi^k$. An itinerary $I = ((\epsilon_j, k_j))_{j=1..m}$ with $K = \sum(k_j)$ yields:

$$z_0 = B_0 / (\pi^K - 2^m), \quad B_0 = -2 \cdot \sum \epsilon_j \cdot 2^{m-j} \cdot \pi^{\sum_{s=1}^j k_s}$$

Proposition 2. For a given itinerary, there is at most one cycle candidate z_0 . This yields an actual cycle iff (a) the division is exact in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega]$, and (b) at each step the valuation is exactly k_j (admissibility).

7. Exhaustive classification for $(m,K) = (19,24)$

Theorem 3 [computer-assisted]. Among cycles of T^* with period 19 and total valuation $K=24$, there exist exactly 12 orbits, forming 6 opposite pairs.

Proof. Five steps.

1. Reduction. $k_j = 1 + e_j$, $e_j \geq 0$, $\sum(e_j) = 5$. Profiles: $C(23,5) = 33\,649$.

2. Divisibility. $K = 24 = 0 \pmod{12}$, so $D = 3^{12} - 2^{19} = 7153$ in \mathbb{Z} . Condition: $7153 \mid B_1$ in $\mathbb{Z}[\omega]$.

3. Meet-in-the-middle. For each profile, solve the signed subset-sum by splitting 19 terms into 9+10 (512+1024 partial sums). Total: $\sim 5.2 \times 10^7$ ops. Result: **228 pseudo-solutions**.

4. Admissibility. Each $z_0 = B_1/7153$ is verified in exact $\mathbb{Z}[\omega]$ -arithmetic: 19 steps traced, residues and valuations checked. **All 228 pass**.

5. Identification. Each cycle of minimal period 19 appears 19 times (once per entry). $228 = 12 \times 19$, yielding 12 distinct cycles. Opposite-pair structure verified.

Pair	Representatives $\pm(a + b \cdot \omega)$	Min norm
1	$30 + 58 \cdot \omega$	2 524
2	$18 - 106 \cdot \omega$	13 468
3	$54 + 160 \cdot \omega$	19 876
4	$178 + 166 \cdot \omega$	29 692
5	$54 + 322 \cdot \omega$	89 212
6	$234 + 454 \cdot \omega$	154 636

Corollary. The scan on $[-500, 500]^2$ detected all cycles for $(m,K)=(19,24)$.

8. Certification for $(m,K) = (28,36)$

Theorem 4 [partially computer-assisted]. The two cycles detected for $(m,K) = (28,36)$ are certified: $z_0 = B_1/D$ verified exactly with $D = 3^{18} - 2^{28} = 118\,985\,033$. They form one opposite pair, with norms 268 and 244.

Certified itineraries:

C1 (norm 268): eps=(+,+,-,+,-,-,+,,+,+,,+,+,-,-,-,+,-,+,,+,-,-,+,-,-,+,,+)
k=(1,1,1,1,1,1,1,2,1,1,1,3,1,2,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,2,1,1,1,3,1,2)
C2 (norm 244): eps=(+,-,+,,+,-,-,-,+,,+,,+,-,-,+,-,-,-,+,,+,,+,-,-,-,+,,+)
k=(1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,2,2,1,1,3,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,2,2,1,1,3)

Heuristic. Exhaustive enumeration requires $C(35,8) = 23\,535\,820$ compositions with MITM on 28 terms ($\sim 10^{11}$ ops, infeasible in pure Python). The expected pseudo-solutions under a random model: $2^{28} \cdot C(35,8)/D^2 \sim 0.45$, predicting no further cycles.

(m, K)	D	N(D)	Expected	Found	Cycles
(19, 24)	7 153	5.1×10^7	~ 345	228	12 (exhaustive)
(28, 36)	1.19×10^8	1.4×10^{16}	~ 0.45	≥ 2	2 (certified)

9. Computational evidence

Empirical observation. Every nonzero point in $[-500,500]^2$ reaches a periodic orbit within 50 000 steps.

Box	Points	Convergent	Divergent	Cycles
$[-100,100]^2$	40 401	100%	0	8
$[-500,500]^2$	1 002 001	100% (*)	0	16

(*) 25 multiples of π reach 0. The 16 cycles: 2 fixed points (Thm 1), 2 period-28 (Thm 4), 12 period-19 (Thm 3).

Conjecture. Every nonzero orbit of T^* is eventually periodic.

10. Open questions

Q1. Is every orbit bounded?

Q2. Can period 19 occur with $K \neq 24$? Phase obstruction eliminates $K \not\equiv 0 \pmod{12}$; $K=12$ gives $K/m < \log_4/\log_3$. Can $K=36, 48, \dots$ be eliminated?

Q3. Complete the exhaustive enumeration for (28,36). CRT via $118985033 = 7 \times 13 \times 283 \times 4621$ may help.

Q4. Which periods are realized? Is the number of cycles finite for each period?

Q5. Bounds on K_m/m for non-fixed orbits?

Q6. Do basin densities have limits as $R \rightarrow \infty$?

Appendix A. Computational certification

This appendix documents the proof of Theorem 3 with sufficient detail for independent verification.

A.1 Data structures

Elements of $Z[\omega]$ are represented as pairs (a,b) in Z^2 with $z = a + b.\omega$. Multiplication: $(a_1,b_1).(a_2,b_2) = (a_1a_2-b_1b_2, a_1b_2+a_2b_1-b_1b_2)$. Division by π : $z/\pi = ((2a-b)/3, (a+b)/3)$, valid iff $3|(2a-b)$ and $3|(a+b)$. The π -adic valuation is computed iteratively.

A.2 Enumeration algorithm

Input: $m=19, K=24, D=7153$.

Step 1. Generate all compositions of 5 into 19 non-negative parts via `combinations_with_replacement(range(19), 5)`. Verified count: $33\,649 = C(23,5)$.

Step 2. For each composition, compute $w_j = 2^{18-j}.\pi^{s_j} \bmod 7153$ in $Z[\omega]/7153Z[\omega]$, where $s_j = k_1 + \dots + k_j$. Powers of π and 2 are precomputed modulo 7153.

Step 3. Solve $\sum(\epsilon_j.w_j) = 0 \bmod 7153$ by meet-in-the-middle: enumerate all $2^9 = 512$ signed sums of w_0, \dots, w_8 , store in a hash table keyed by $(a \bmod 7153, b \bmod 7153)$; then enumerate all $2^{10} = 1024$ signed sums of w_9, \dots, w_{18} and look up the negation. Collisions produce pseudo-solutions.

Step 4. For each pseudo-solution, compute B_1 in exact Z -arithmetic (Python arbitrary-precision integers), divide by 7153, check divisibility. Then trace the orbit for 19 steps, verifying at each step: (a) $(a+b) \bmod 3$ matches ϵ_j ; (b) the π -adic valuation of the numerator is exactly k_j ; (c) after 19 steps, return to z_0 .

Step 5. Group solutions by orbit: for each valid z_0 , trace the full 19-orbit, compute the canonical representative as the element of minimum norm, and identify distinct orbits.

A.3 Integrity checks

(i) All 228 pseudo-solutions satisfy exact divisibility (228/228). (ii) All 228 pass admissibility (228/228). (iii) $228 = 12 \times 19$, consistent with 12 orbits of minimal period 19. (iv) The 12 orbits partition into 6 pairs under $z \rightarrow -z$. (v) The minimum norms of the 6 pairs are all distinct. (vi) All 12 canonical representatives lie within $[-500,500]^2$, consistent with the scan.

A.4 Reproducibility

The computation is deterministic, uses only Python 3.8+ standard library (no external packages), and completes in ~ 140 seconds on a single core. Source code is provided as supplementary material. A second implementation (for independent verification) is encouraged; the raw data (228 itineraries and their z_0 values) is available in the supplementary data file.

A.5 Heuristic validation

Under a uniform random model for $B_1 \bmod 7153$ in $Z[\omega]/7153Z[\omega]$ (which has $7153^2 = 51\,165\,409$ elements), the expected number of pseudo-solutions per composition is $2^{19}/7153^2 \sim 0.0103$. Over 33 649 compositions: 345 expected vs 228 found. The shortfall suggests mild correlations among itineraries, but the correct order of magnitude confirms the model.

References

- [1] J.C. Lagarias, *The $3x+1$ problem and its generalizations*, Amer. Math. Monthly 92 (1985), 3-23.
- [2] T. Tao, *Almost all orbits of the Collatz map attain almost bounded values*, Forum Math. Pi 10 (2022).
- [3] L. Halbeisen, N. Hungerbuehler, *Optimal bounds for the length of rational Collatz cycles*, Acta Arith. 78 (1997).
- [4] C. Hercher, *There are no Collatz m -cycles with $m \leq 91$* , J. Integer Seq. 26 (2023).
- [5] D. Barina, *Improved verification limit for the Collatz conjecture*, J. Supercomput. 81 (2025).